

The Island Sea Problem

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ABSTRACT: Significant changes are taking place in the environment of our planet today as a result of the negative impact of human activities. In particular, climate change and various natural disasters are felt in all latitudes of the planet. As a result, forested areas are shrinking, polluting the atmosphere, water and lithosphere.

KEYWORDS: island problem, desert, area, ecology, danger, Island Sea, water level, pressure, local problem, regional problem.

INTRODUCTION

Changes in the state of the natural environment under human influence, strong anthropogenic impact on living and non-living components, cause local, regional and global environmental problems. In particular, similar effects have led to the "Aral Sea problem", which is considered the most dangerous point of the ecological crisis in the region. The following data proves our point. Due to the rapid development of irrigation in Central Asia since 1961, the volume of water flowing into it has been declining from year to year, and since 2005 the Amudarya has completely stopped flowing into the Aral Sea. Due to the constant natural evaporation, its level has dropped catastrophically. At the end of 2013, its level was returned to an absolute height of 23.5 m (53 m in 1961). As a result, 55,000 square kilometers of land were built and turned into land. Since the water level of the Aral Sea depends on the regime of the Amudarya and Sirdarya rivers, the more water is used for irrigation, the less water there is in the sea. In particular, as a result of the expansion of irrigated arable land since the 1960s, the amount of water flowing into the sea from the Amudarya and Sirdarya has decreased from year to year. As a result, sea levels began to fall sharply. [1]

Table 1. The impact of declining water levels in the Aral Sea on its water surface and water capacity

Years	Water level m	Area km kv	Water capacity km cub
1960	53,40	68900	1063
1976	48,27	55700	730
1991	37,70	35100	302
1994	36,60	32500	250
1997	36,60	32500	250
2000	33,22	23900	167
2001	32,11	21100	142
2002	30,9	18100	119

The decline in the water level in the Aral Sea also had a sharp impact on the values of the elements of water balance: in 1911-1960 the average sea level was 53.04 m (in the Baltic system), the amount of water flowing into the sea by rivers was 56 cubic km, The amount of precipitation on the surface was 9.1 km. cub Consumption, consumption, consisted mainly of evaporation, which averaged 66.1 km cub during the period. During this period, there was a negative difference in the water balance: the sea lost 1 km cub per year, and from 1911 to 1960 it lost 50 km cub.

Table 2. Water balance of the Aral Sea for different accounting periods (cub km / year)

Accounting period (years)	Income		Expenditure	Difference
	Amudarya and Inflow of Sirdarya water flow	Rainfall	discard?	discard?
Amudarya and Inflow of Sirdarya water flow	56,00	9,10	66,10	-1,00

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1911-1960	43,30	8,00	65,40	-14,10
1961-1970	16,70	6,30	55,20	-32,20
1971-1980	3,90	6,20	43,70	-33,60
1981-1990	21,00	4,60	33,60	-8,00
1991-1994	13,66	4,27	22,7	-4,77
1996-2000	56,00	9,10	66,10	-1,00

Currently, the Aral Sea is divided into 3 parts: the first - the small and shallow northern part (salinity 8-13 g / l); the second has a relatively large area and a shallow eastern part (salinity 69-72 g / l); the third is the deepest western part (salinity 68-69 g / l). [2]

Dynamics of construction of the Aral Sea Due to the rapid development of irrigation in Central Asia over the years, the Amudarya and Sirdarya rivers flowing into the Aral Sea are declining and more than 40,000 km² of the Aral Sea is turning dry due to high natural evaporation. Resulting in the late twentieth century. The land is characterized by a typical sandy-sandy desert. The desert surface is a sloping plain in the central part of the Aral Sea, where mainly eolian relief forms (dunes, sands 0.5-4 m) and sandstones are distributed. The desert consists of sand-gravel, sand, gravel, and mud formed in the delta, sea, and lake conditions. Located in the subtropical latitudes, the climate is sharply continental. The average annual temperature is 9.6 °, in January 7 °, in July 25.7 °, and the annual rainfall is 88 mm. The depth of groundwater. 7-10 m, mineralization 30-80 g / l.

The desert is mainly covered with shallow sediments. Black saxaul, cherkez, yulgun, shura are found in areas with sparse vegetation and eolian sand relief, and yulgun, sar-sazan, shura are found in areas with shallow sandy soils. The desert is inhabited by animals (mostly rodents) that have invaded the surrounding area. In the south, deposits of industrial importance, such as sulfur salts and natural gas, have been discovered. First Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan Rustam Azimov congratulated the 1st President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov on the Aral Sea problems, their gene pool, their impact on flora and fauna and the international conference on mitigation measures. Read aloud. The conference brought together representatives from more than 20 countries, including Central Asia, Germany, Greece, Israel, India, China, the Netherlands, Russia, Japan and other countries, international and regional organizations, financial institutions, environmental, climate change and water resources. Well-known scientists and experts in the field of management participated. Today, millions of people on the planet suffer from a shortage of clean drinking water. This is especially evident in arid countries. Deterioration of the ecological situation in the Aral Sea region has led to ecological imbalances in the region, exacerbating water scarcity. This has a negative impact on the socio-economic development of the region, the living conditions and health of the population, biodiversity. Therefore, this problem requires strengthening cooperation between the countries of the region and international organizations. Bolat Nurgaliyev, Secretary General of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), Sergey Lebedev, Chairman of the CIS Executive Committee, and Katsuji Matsunami, Director of the Asian Development Bank's Department for Agriculture and Natural Resources in Central and West Asia, spoke at the opening of the international conference. , Annette Dixon, Director of the World Bank Regional Office for Central Asia, Nedret Emiroglu, Regional Director for Health Programs of the World Health Organization, Sanjiv Kumar, UNICEF Regional Adviser on Health and Nutrition , Alain Mushiru, UNFPA Regional Director for Europe and Central Asia, Gjegosh Donochik, Director of the UNIDO Regional Office for Europe and the CIS, Matsuyoshi Kawasaki, Deputy Managing Director, Regional Office of the Japan International Cooperation Agency, Yanik Glemar, GEJ / UNDP Executive Coordinator they shouted. In the second half of the twentieth century and the beginning of the twenty-first century, a number of global problems arose, and the further development of mankind depended on the solution of these problems. Global issues cover all aspects of human life, world politics, economics, interstate and interethnic relations. One of the most important global issues of recent times is environmental issues. As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov noted at the UN summit, the problem of the drying Aral Sea is a problem of millions of people living in the region, who hope for help from such an influential organization as the United Nations. This issue cannot be ignored. When it comes to the fate of millions of people, it is time to abandon old views and take a new approach to the issue. It is necessary to use water wisely, taking into account the interests of all peoples in the flow of Transboundary Rivers. It is necessary to abandon the spiritually outdated projects of the last century, which do not meet the requirements of the times, and strictly follow the laws of ecology in the construction of hydraulic structures. If we continue to act against the laws of nature today, there will be even bigger and more serious problems in the future. The environmental problem is not the state border, it is the border of another region. If left unchecked, it will become increasingly global and cover a wider area. Each of us must have a deep understanding of this simple truth and act accordingly. We are very pleased that Uzbekistan's position in the international arena is strengthening and gaining a foothold. We are all proud that a special resolution on the declaration of the Aral Sea region as a zone of ecological innovation and technology on the basis of a proposal made by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 75th session of the UN General Assembly was adopted unanimously. [3]

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In fact, this proposal was consistently put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev. The initiative was first put forward by the head of our state in August 2018 at a meeting of the heads of the founding states of the International Fund for Saving the Aral Sea in Turkmenbashi. Speaking at the 75th session of the UN General Assembly in September last year, the head of state called on the member states of this influential international organization to develop and adopt a special resolution on this issue.[4]

CONCLUSION

This was not just a call, but a full disclosure of the meaning and significance of the forthcoming resolution. In other words, the document provides for the creation of conditions for investment in the creation and implementation of high-tech innovations, environmentally friendly, energy and water-saving technologies, the widespread use of "green economy", prevention of soil degradation, desertification and ecological migration, ecotourism. It was said that measures on topical issues should be covered. Significant work is being done in our country to mitigate the negative impact of the Aral Sea tragedy on the health of the Aral Sea population and the environment. The easiest and cheapest way to stabilize the ecological environment of the Aral Sea region is to establish forests. The dry part of the sea is 5.5 million hectares, of which 3.5 million are in our territory. If we can turn 2 million hectares of it into forests, the situation will be much better. To do this, it is necessary to take measures to turn 100,000 hectares of forests every year. If we work hard in this way and the dry part of the sea is covered with greenery, we can eliminate the risk of this problem in 15-20 years. The conference has a practical value in this regard, as the proposals, ideas and investments expressed in it are aimed at stabilizing the climate of the Aral Sea region.

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